

D9.2 Gender Equity Policy

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Executive summary

This Deliverable gives details of the gender action plan which will be applied throughout the Fatigue4Light project. It lists the actions and activities which will be carried out. Updated information related to the impact of the plan and the technologies will be provided in the final report. This Deliverable underpins the project objectives; considerations of gender and diversity aspects will ensure that there are no barriers to the best candidates being chosen to work on the project and later in industry.

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List of abbreviations

<i>EC</i>	<i>European Commission</i>
<i>EU</i>	<i>European Union</i>
<i>FP6</i>	<i>6th Framework Programme</i>
<i>Ga</i>	<i>General Assembly</i>
<i>GA</i>	<i>Grant Agreement</i>
<i>GAP</i>	<i>Gender Action Plan</i>
<i>S&T</i>	<i>Science & Technology</i>

Introduction

There are two parts to the consideration of gender in Fatigue4Light. The goal of the gender action plan is to strengthen any gender-specific aspects of the scientific and technical research and to act on the gender-equality elements of the Commission's strategy.

Ethical and Gender aspects have already been considered in the formation of this proposal but over the duration of the project, it is possible that changes to partner representatives will occur; it is important that these factors are reviewed at regular intervals during the life-cycle of the project. Therefore, a snapshot of the gender balance will be taken every six months.

A study by UNESCO shows that cultural, economic and educational shortcomings have led to the marginalisation of women in all scientific domains, especially those related to engineering. Current patriarchal cultures and traditional religious roles for women can discourage them from pursuing scientific careers and there is a lack of high-profile women who would serve as role models.

The dynamics for female exclusion and integration are opaque and not easily quantified. Although direct discrimination is illegal, indirect discrimination has not been eliminated but is difficult to identify and modify and will, in many cases, involve a change in working culture. Additionally, some responsibilities, such as caring roles, which have traditionally been seen as being solely applicable to women, can affect everyone. Actions such as flexible working hours and family friendly policies are clearly of equal benefit to all staff on the project.

While no barriers to women performing any of the research in Fatigue4Light have been identified, positive steps must be taken to promote women within the project, ensure equality in decision-making roles and to ensure that potential gender-issues within the research are properly addressed.

Today, the European Commission (EC) undertakes to promote equal opportunities and achieve well-balanced gender distribution within the European-funded research and innovation projects. Since the 6th Framework Programme (FP6), all projects have been required to incorporate a Gender Action Plan (GAP), the aim of which is to promote participation by women in research. Furthermore, by integrating the concept of gender mainstreaming into EU projects, the Commission aims to ensure that gender aspects are taken into consideration during the whole research and innovation project, from its inception until delivery, and to ensure that the scientific research addresses women's needs, as much as men's needs, in order to eliminate gender discrimination.

Further information with respect to the EC activities and policies to promote gender equality in science is available at:

<http://ec.europa.eu/programmes/horizon2020/en/h2020-section/promoting-gender-equality-research-and-innovation>

- **Attainment of the objectives and explanation of deviations**

The deliverable is fully in line with the contractual obligations and the project objectives. There is no time and content deviation.

1. Women in Engineering

A report [1] on the effect of the 2006 – 2010 European gender strategy shows that progress towards equality was greater in areas which were not systematically tackled in previous years and where the link to the EU2020 strategy was weak. Gender mainstreaming is also far from being achieved and damaging stereotypes still persist and should be tackled by targeting both genders through both traditional and social media. While women make up 46% of post-graduates in the EU, they only make up 28% of post-graduates in subjects such as engineering, manufacturing and construction [2]. The EU's strategic engagement report [3] states that promoting gender equality is a core activity for the EU and a driver of economic growth, and that promoting equality will be carried out in all its activities. Within research organisations, barriers to equality should be removed and gender equality plans put in place. The EU is also collecting data on women in decision-making positions, with the aim of creating a gender corridor where there are at least 40% of any one gender in these roles. It is also important to assess the impact of these EU actions on both men and women to ensure that they benefit equally.

The number of women with a career in research is slowly growing in Europe. Still, they remain significantly underrepresented. When analysing the differences between She Figures 2015 [2] and She Figures 2018 [4] a positive, if slow, evolution is seen.

Specifically, The She Figures 2018 [4] highlights that on average, women now outnumber men at student and graduate levels and there is broad gender balance at PhD level. However, their distribution in the different scientific fields of study remains uneven, which shows the persistence of gender stereotypes.

The presence of stereotypes is especially strong in the field of science, technology, engineering and mathematics (STEM), where women remain underrepresented at all levels starting as students (32% at Bachelor, Master or equivalent level) up to top academic positions (15%). Furthermore, women still make up the minority of top academic positions.

The EU's guide to gender equality in H2020 [5] gives three main objectives for the programme:

- Fostering gender balance in research teams
- Ensuring gender balance in decision-making
- Integrating gender / sex analysis in research and innovation

The Commission will therefore monitor and evaluate the gender dimension in research projects. This is started at the proposal stage, where applicants give the gender of the people carrying out the proposed research and is updated in subsequent periodic reports. Where relevant, projects will be asked to show how sex / gender has been taken into account. It is also written into the grant agreement that beneficiaries “must take all measures to promote equal opportunities between men and women in the implementation of the action” and “must aim, to the extent possible, for a gender balance at all levels of personnel assigned to the action, including at supervisory and managerial level”. Where appropriate, gender training is eligible as an activity in the grant.

The European Commission conducted its own review of FP7 funded research; the seventh monitoring report [6] shows that there has been some progress regarding gender equality in the participation in FP7. Women represent 20.04% of individuals characterized as “contact persons for scientific aspects” in signed grant agreements, up from 17% in FP6 [7]. Despite the increase in women's participation, compared to previous Framework Programmes, the set target of 40% for all programmes and projects is still a long way from being reached.

2. Gender Equity in Fatigue4Light

Among the 40 participants involved in Fatigue4Light, 7 are women. All women are highly educated with at minimum a Bachelor Degree.

Their role in the frame of the Fatigue4Light in M2 is described in the table below:

Name	Fatigue4Light role	Degree	Skills/ Background
Lucia Gratiela Barbu	Project Coordinator	Ph.D	Computational Mechanics, nonlinear modelling, Finite Element Analysis, Project Management
Alicia Pallarés Monfort	Financial Manager, WP9 participant	Master Degree	Project Management, EU policy, Financial aspects
Lucia Arevalo	WP10 participant	Master Degree	Communication y digital marketing
Marina Presas	WP10 Leader	Bachelor Degree	Communication and Dissemination
Sara Di Lisio	WP1, WP3, WP6, WP7 participant	Master Degree	Senior Technical Specialist, Automotive chassis, suspension
Magdalena Juntikka	WP1, WP3, WP4, WP6, WP7, WP8 participant	Ph. D	Sustainability, Eco-design, polymers
Giulia Fratesi	WP1, WP2, WP3, WP4	Master Degree	Administrative and financial management

Table 1: Female personnel involved in the Fatigue4Light project in M2

This “Gender Equity Policy” outlines the plan of the Fatigue4Light consortium to promote and encourage gender equality throughout the lifetime of the project and beyond. Indeed, the plan has been conceived as a “chart” proposing several awareness actions and good practices. The partners will get acquainted with the document whereas the General Assembly members will be asked to explicitly show their adherence¹ to the “Gender Equity Policy” upon a specific request made during the M06 General Assembly Meeting.

Nevertheless, it is important to specify that the plan does not contain any quantitative indicators. This voluntary approach corresponds to the concern for keeping a balance between the project’s international and multicultural consortium, the gender equality policies in place in the beneficiaries’ organisations and in their respective countries. Thus, the “Gender Equity Policy” provides support and guidelines rather than binding measures.

The Fatigue4Light “Gender Equity Policy” will have a strong role in ensuring that fairness and equality of opportunities exist within the project and are promoted by the partners. This plan incorporates actions designed around three main objectives:

1. Ensure that a women-friendly environment exists within Fatigue4Light;
2. Contribute to the development of gender-sensitive science;
3. Promote women’s leadership positions in science and technology.

The topics addressed and the work performed in the Fatigue4Light project are completely gender neutral; they can be carried out equally well by women or men. Similarly, the results of the project will be of benefit for both genders.

3. Gender Equity Actions

While operating in the spirit of gender equality, the Fatigue4Light consortium will attempt to address the gender-bias through several specific actions developed around the three main objectives:

<p>Objective n°1: Ensure that a women-friendly environment exists within Fatigue4Light</p>	<p>Specific actions:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Change culture and behaviour by discouraging any use of inappropriate language or discussion with an implied stereotyping or gender-bias. Promote work-life balance by encouraging, where appropriate and compatible with delivery of S&T outputs within the time constraints of the GA, to offer the opportunity for flexible working hours, home-working, job-sharing and other family-friendly employment practices to all staff. Support early-stage career development by involving early-stage female researchers in the practice and management of research tasks.
<p>Objective n°2: Contribute to the development gender-sensitive science</p>	<p>Specific actions:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Overcome gender stereotypes by avoiding that female- or male - gendered representations guide decisions about the attribution of tasks. Acknowledge women's visions and expectations by fully taking into account women's points of view, suggestions.
<p>Objective n°3 : Promote women's leadership positions in science and technology</p>	<p>Specific actions:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Support women to attain key positions in the practice of research and in key managerial positions by regular diffusion of information on high-profile women researchers and on available opportunities. Strengthen women's visibility and their role in communication by promoting female researchers presence in the flow of scientific communication (participation in conferences, publications in peer-reviewed journals...).

Conclusions

The action patterns presented above are to become an expression of the partners' commitment to spread awareness of the gender equality issues. As already stated earlier, this document provides non-binding guidelines which can perfectly complete existing measures and gender equality strategies. The partners will get acquainted with the document whereas the General Assembly members will be asked to explicitly show their adherence¹ to the "Gender Equity Policy" upon a specific request made during the M06 General Assembly Meeting.

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¹ The explicit adherence will be provided in the form of an e-mail notification

